

Mercury(II) Thiosalicylic Acid(TSA) Complexes with Nitrogen and Sulfur Donor Ligands

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Eight complexes of Mercury(II) having the composition $Hg_2L_2Cl_2B_2$, where L is TSA and B is nitrogen or sulfur donor ligand viz : γ -picoline, pyridine, 4-aminopyridine, piperidine, quinoline, isoquinoline, morpholine and thiourea have been reported. The complexes are found to be of tetrahedral configuration involving bridging chloride groups from the analysis, conductance and infrared spectral studies.

THIOSALICYLIC acid has invoked a lot of interest as a ligand in recent years since in addition to the oxygen atom, (either carbonyl oxygen or hydroxyl oxygen of -COOH group) it has the sulfur atom as a potential donor site. Though the complex forming ability of this ligand with many metal ions has been studied¹⁻⁵ in solution state, very little work has been done in the solid state. Only recently Nigam *et al.*⁶ have studied its complexes with some metal ions. We have been studying^{7,8} the complexes of *o*-hydroxy aryl carbonyl compounds (including salicylates) with divalent metal ions. Among the divalent metal ions Mercury (II) has considerable affinity for sulfur donors as evidenced from its stable complexes with thiourea⁹ and substituted thioureas¹⁰. Thiosalicylic acid attracted our attention as it contains both oxygen and sulfur donor atoms and we thought it worthwhile to study the preferential bonding of Mercury(II) ion with one or both the donors. As a result, this communication reports eight mixed ligand complexes of the composition $Hg_2L_2Cl_2B_2$ where L = TSA and B is either a nitrogen or sulfur donor ligand.

Experimental

Preparation of Mercury(II) (TSA) complex

An ethanolic solution of thiosalicylic acid was added in stoichiometric ratio to an aqueous solution of mercuric chloride followed by dropwise addition of ammonia. The white precipitate separated was suction filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Preparation of mixed ligand complexes

The mixed ligand complexes were prepared by refluxing $Hg(TSA)$ complex in ethanol medium with γ -picoline, pyridine, 4-aminopyridine, morpholine, piperidine, quinoline, isoquinoline and thiourea separately for about 20 minutes. On cooling the compounds separated out which were filtered

under suction, washed with absolute ethanol, ether and dried *in vacuo*.

The composition of the complexes was established by estimating the metal complexometrically by titrating with EDTA using Erichrome Black-T as indicator in the pH range 10 and chloride by gravimetric procedure and nitrogen by Duma's method. Infrared spectra in the range 5000-640 cm^{-1} were recorded in Nujol mulls using SP-200 double beam spectrophotometer. Molar conductance was measured in $10^{-3}M$ acetone solution using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Analytical, conductance data and principal i.r. absorption bands are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Mercury(II) ion has a $5d^{10}$ configuration and hence forms tetrahedral complexes involving $6s6p^3$ hybrid orbitals for bonding, leaving a perfectly non-bonding shell ($d, 4d, s$) which causes least perturbation to the preferred stereochemistry. All the Mercury(II) complexes reported in the present investigation have the general composition $Hg_2L_2Cl_2B_2$ from their analysis. These are white amorphous solids having comparatively low solubility in common organic solvents and have relatively high melting points. Molar conductance values in acetone medium are very low indicating non-electrolytic nature of the complexes and suggesting covalent bonding for the chloride groups. All the complexes are highly soluble in alkali forming sodium salts which indicates that the carbonyl group is free and not linked to the metal atom.

Study of infrared spectra of thiosalicylic acid, Mercury(II) complex of TSA and the mixed ligand complexes is informative. Though the S-H vibration is characteristically weak and may go often undetected in the spectra of thin films, S-H stretching frequency appeared as a band of medium intensity at 2500 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of thiosalicylic acid. In Mercury(II) TSA complex and also in the

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, M.P., CONDUCTANCE AND INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF Hg(II) COMPLEXES (cm⁻¹)

Compound	M.P. (°C)	Λ_M mhos.cm ²	% Hg		% Cl		% Nitrogen		Infrared spectra $\nu(\text{C-S})$
			Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
TSA									660(s), 700(sh)
Hg(TSA) ₂ Cl ₂					12.00	12.24			660(s), 676(sh)
Hg ₂ L ₂ Cl ₂ (γ -Pic) ₂	265	2.1	41.25	41.70	10.72	10.93	2.85	2.90	650(s), 700(m)
Hg ₂ L ₂ Cl ₂ (Py) ₂	220	2.4	42.10	42.90	11.16	11.42	2.86	2.99	650(s), 690(sh)
Hg ₂ L ₂ Cl ₂ (4-Ampy) ₂	250	2.1	40.9	41.6	10.56	10.74	2.68	2.80	650(s), 690(m)
Hg ₂ L ₂ Cl ₂ (Morpholine) ₂	178	3.4	42.0	42.2	10.24	10.46	2.84	2.94	640(s), 680(m)
Hg ₂ L ₂ Cl ₂ (Pipe) ₂	155	3.6	43.0	43.4	11.0	11.2	2.89	2.95	650(s), 700(m)
Hg ₂ L ₂ Cl ₂ (Q) ₂	285	4.0	38.2	38.8	9.62	9.71	2.67	2.70	660(s), 690(sh)
Hg ₂ L ₂ Cl ₂ (I.Q) ₂	173	4.6	38.4	38.8	9.50	9.71	2.62	2.70	640(s), 680(m)
Hg ₂ L ₂ Cl ₂ (tu) ₂	225	4.5	43.0	43.2	11.12	11.36	5.98	6.02	660(s), 680(m)

γ -Pic = γ -Picoline, Py = Pyridine, 4-Ampy = 4-Amino pyridine, Pipe = Piperidine, Q = Quinoline, I.Q = Isoquinoline, tu = thiourea.

mixed ligand complexes the absorption band due to $\nu(\text{S-H})$ is not observed. The disappearance of this band is attributed to sulfhydryl group coordination to the metal ion, as reported by some other workers⁶. Two other bands appear in the 600–700 cm⁻¹ region [at 660(s) and 700(sh) in TSA] assignable to $\nu(\text{C-S})$ which shift in the complexes. The other assignable principal bands are around 1600 cm⁻¹ and 3200 cm⁻¹ attributable to carbonyl and hydroxyl absorptions which remain unaffected in the complexes. C-H stretching frequency appears around 2900 cm⁻¹ in the acid and the complexes. Direct evidence for metal-ligand bonding could not be obtained as $\nu(\text{M-S})$ and $\nu(\text{M-N})$ are beyond the range of spectrophotometer used. However, information regarding bonding of nitrogen ligands and thiourea is obtained by finger print technique as most of the absorption bands due to free ligand are shifted. Assignments could not be made definitely as there is considerable overlapping of bands due to the acid and the ligands.

Hence the complexes reported in the present investigation have tetrahedral environment, the

tetra-coordination is achieved by dimerisation involving bridging chloride groups and provide evidence for preferential bonding via—sulfur atom in case of Hg(II) ion.

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